

Table 3. Summary of measurement of sleep quality, cortisol and cardiovascular among healthcare shift workers of the included studies.

Author	Sample size(<i>n</i>)	Exposure of working shift	Cortisol measure	Cardiovascular measure	Sleep quality measure	Outcome	Conclusions
Roy ²⁵ , 2023 (India)	120 healthcare providers: 60 fixed duty & 60 shift duty	Fixed time schedule: 10.00-17.00 (Monday to Friday) Shift duty schedule: Two mornings (6:00-14:00), Two evening (14:00-22:00), Two-night duties (22:00-6:00)	Blood	HRV (SDNN, RMSSD, pNN50, mean HR)	Athens Insomnia Scale	<p>Cortisol result: Shift duty workers had significantly high evening cortisol level (9.4±2.36 mcg/dL) than fixed duty workers (3.74±1.7 mcg/dL) (p=0.036).</p> <p>Cardiovascular result: Low HF power. LF/HF ratio significantly higher (p<0.001) in shift workers</p> <p>Sleep result: Shift duty workers had higher chance of having insomnia (Athen's score >6) significantly (p<0.001) than fixed duty workers.</p>	Long duration of shift work increases evening cortisol level, higher chance having insomnia and impaired cardiovascular regulation.

Abbreviations: Standard Deviation of all normal-to-normal (SDNN) intervals; Root Mean Square of Successive Differences (RMSSD) intervals; Number of successive NN pairs differing by more than 50 ms(NN50); Percentage of NN intervals differing by greater than 50 ms (pNN50); **Heart Rate (HR)**